

COMPUTER SCIENCE

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<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.14956604>

ANALYSIS OF APPROACHES TO MODELING UNCERTAINTY IN LOGISTICS INFORMATION SYSTEMS

Abstract.

The article examines uncertainty modeling in logistics information systems, focusing on stochastic, statistical, interval-based, and fuzzy methods. Their applications in transport flow management, demand forecasting, and resource optimization are analyzed. Integration into modern software is explored: statistical methods in PostgreSQL, stochastic modeling in AnyLogic, interval-based approaches in MATLAB and Python, and fuzzy algorithms via scikit-fuzzy. The choice depends on uncertainty type, computational resources, and accuracy needs. Statistical models handle large datasets, stochastic methods model complex scenarios, interval-based techniques ensure stability, and fuzzy systems support subjective decision-making. Future research should develop hybrid approaches and apply machine learning for optimal method selection.

Keywords: uncertainty modeling; logistics information systems; stochastic methods; interval analysis; fuzzy logic

Problem statement. Modern logistics systems use mathematical methods for planning and optimization, but real-world uncertainty complicates classical deterministic approaches. Uncertainty stems from transport conditions, delays, demand fluctuations, weather, and data limitations.

Traditional algorithms assume fixed values, reducing accuracy. Effective transport flow management requires methods that model uncertainty and ensure solution stability. Computer science offers stochastic, statistical, interval-based, and fuzzy approaches for adapting to variable parameters [1].

The key challenge is developing efficient uncertainty representation methods for integration into logistics systems, improving accuracy and adaptability. While various modeling approaches exist, their seamless integration remains an open issue.

Review of research and publications. Various approaches to representing uncertainty in logistics problems have been explored in numerous scientific studies. In [2], stochastic and statistical modeling in logistics information systems is analyzed. The authors state that stochastic modeling is suitable for problems where uncertainty has a random nature, while statistical methods are effective for processing historical data and making predictions.

Another approach is presented in [3], where interval-based methods for solving transportation problems

are examined. These methods allow working with a broad range of possible values, making them suitable for scenarios with high uncertainty levels. Their advantage lies in providing guaranteed solution estimates even with limited information.

Thus, despite the diversity of approaches, the question of their integration into software products and information systems remains open, which could enable automation of decision-making processes in logistics.

Research objective. This study analyzes uncertainty modeling in logistics information systems for automated decision-making and software integration. It focuses on stochastic, statistical, interval-based, and fuzzy methods, assessing their use in transport flow and warehouse logistics. Modern computational tools, including databases, algorithmic libraries, and machine learning, are also evaluated. The results will highlight the advantages and limitations of each approach, aiding the development of algorithms and software for managing uncertainty in logistics.

Methods of representing uncertainty in logistics information systems. Different approaches to representing uncertainty in logistics information systems can be classified into stochastic, statistical, interval-based, and fuzzy methods (Fig. 1). Each of these approaches has unique characteristics and is applied in different scenarios depending on the nature of uncertainty and the available data.

Figure 1. – Classification of Uncertainty Representation Methods in Logistics Information Systems

Stochastic methods rely on probability theory to model uncertainty. In these approaches, input parameters are described as random variables or probability distributions. Stochastic models are used when event probabilities can be estimated, such as predicting delivery times under random delays. These models are typically integrated into logistics information systems through statistical analysis libraries such as SciPy in Python [4].

Statistical methods use historical data to analyze patterns and make predictions. Regression models and machine learning techniques, for example, can estimate product demand or determine optimal inventory levels in warehouse systems. The advantage of statistical methods is their ability to adapt to changing conditions by learning from real data. Databases such as PostgreSQL support statistical functions for processing information in logistics systems [5].

Interval-based methods represent uncertain parameters using interval values instead of specific numbers. This allows for obtaining guaranteed solution estimates when precise probabilities are unknown or difficult to determine. Interval analysis is applied in transportation information systems to assess permissible deviations in delivery times or transportation costs.

Fuzzy methods are based on fuzzy logic, enabling operations with linguistic variables and subjective evaluations, such as "high load level" or "low risk of delay". Implementing fuzzy systems in logistics information systems allows automated decision-making under complex uncertainty conditions. A widely used tool for working with fuzzy models is the scikit-fuzzy library in Python.

Thus, the methods of representing uncertainty differ in modeling approaches and computational complexity. Stochastic and statistical methods are well-suited for analyzing large datasets and machine learning applications, whereas interval-based and fuzzy models are effective for handling imprecise or incomplete data. The choice of method depends on the specific problem conditions, available data, and forecasting accuracy requirements.

Analysis and discussion of results. Different uncertainty representation methods vary in effectiveness for logistics information systems. Stochastic and statistical approaches suit tasks with large historical datasets, enabling probability estimation. Interval-based and

fuzzy methods work when precise values are unavailable but approximate boundaries are needed.

Computational complexity is a key factor. Stochastic models require significant resources for multiple simulations, while statistical methods, such as regression analysis, operate faster and integrate well into databases (e.g., PostgreSQL). Interval-based methods perform within predefined ranges, and fuzzy systems depend on rule base size, affecting performance.

Integration varies: statistical methods fit databases via SQL queries, stochastic approaches suit simulation tools like AnyLogic, interval-based methods work in MATLAB or Python (NumPy), and fuzzy systems use specialized libraries (e.g., scikit-fuzzy).

Thus, method selection depends on task goals, data availability, and computational resources. Statistical methods enable rapid modeling, while stochastic and interval-based approaches handle high variability. Fuzzy models are valuable for automated logistics management in expert systems [6].

Conclusions

This study examined uncertainty modeling in logistics information systems, focusing on stochastic, statistical, interval-based, and fuzzy methods. Each has distinct characteristics suited to specific uncertainty types and computational resources.

Stochastic methods excel in forecasting but demand high computational power. Statistical approaches efficiently handle historical data and integrate well with databases. Interval-based methods address unknown probabilities, while fuzzy models support automated logistics management.

Practical implementation depends on software environments: statistical models fit PostgreSQL, stochastic approaches suit AnyLogic, interval-based methods work in MATLAB/Python, and fuzzy algorithms integrate via scikit-fuzzy.

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